

PEDAGOGY

EFFECTIVE READING STRATEGIES FOR ESP UKRAINIAN STUDENTS

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Abstract

Reading proficiency is a critical skill for professional performance. It enables effective communication, continuous learning, and problem-solving, while also enhancing productivity, career advancement, writing skills, adaptability, and expertise. The necessity for students to develop strong reading skills has motivated Ukrainian educators to implement various techniques in teaching ESP reading and examine the impact of these techniques on enhancing the reading abilities of Ukrainian students. This article discusses recent developments and current issues in acquiring reading skills through strategies that affect teachers and learners and suggests reading strategies needed to develop reading proficiency.

Keywords: reading proficiency, reading strategies, English for Specific Purposes (ESP), Theme-Based Learning (TBL), Task-Based Language Learning.

Introduction

In today's world, proficiency in English is increasingly seen as essential for success in many professional areas, including Information Technology (IT). As modern universities strive to equip their students for the fast-changing IT sector, language teaching within IT programs has become more important than ever.

Today Professionally Oriented English Language Teaching for IT students (POELT) contributes significantly to modern university education by addressing the specific language and communication needs of students pursuing careers in the IT sector. POELT combines elements of ESP and EAP, focusing on the language needs of learners within a specific professional context, such as business, healthcare, engineering, or IT. It integrates both ESP and EAP approaches to address the language needs of professionals to enhance their communication skills, such as reading and writing technical reports, presenting findings, and participating in meetings.

Reading proficiency is an indispensable part of academic and professional success. It goes beyond the ability to decode words on a page; it encompasses comprehension, critical thinking, and the ability to engage with and reflect on complex ideas. Nunung Mardianti (2020) stated that standard reading proficiency requires students to analyze, relate, and critique information within a single source and across multiple sources. Reading at a higher level involves more than just basic comprehension; it requires advanced skills and strategies that enable readers to engage deeply with complex texts.

The study aims to examine context-specific, task-based strategies to improve the language and reading proficiency levels of undergraduate university students at the Computer Science and Cybernetics Faculty of the

Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv in Ukraine.

Research Questions

The specific questions to be answered in this study are:

What are the primary concerns and difficulties in the acquisition of reading skills in teaching ESP?

What strategies should educators implement in their classrooms to improve learners' reading proficiency?

Method

This research is descriptive and focuses on the analysis and classification of cognitive strategies used by the students in reading.

Literature review

Reading strategies have been investigated in a variety of studies by (Oxford & Nyikos, 1989; Anderson, 2003; Mokhtari and Reichard, 2002; Kolic-Vehovec, Bajankiand Zubkovic, 2011; Aydinbek, 2021; Sheorey and Mokhtari (2001), etc.). Sheorey and Mokhtari (2001) divided reading strategies into three primary categories: metacognitive strategies, cognitive strategies, and support strategies. Metacognitive strategies involve techniques that readers use to oversee or regulate their reading. Cognitive strategies encompass actions or procedures, such as reading aloud, adjusting reading speed, and re-reading for improved comprehension used directly with the text. On the other hand, support strategies include tools like using a dictionary, taking notes, and underlining information to better understand a specific text. O'Malley & Chamot (1990) defined cognitive strategies as those that are closely linked to specific learning tasks and are used in the learning process, including repetition, translation, grouping, resourcing, note-taking, deduction, elaboration, imagination, and inference. Ghafournia (2014) states that learning strategy holds a significant role in

enhancing students' ability to comprehend text, perform specified tests, and solve specific problems.

According to Cahyono and Widiati (2006), reading at a higher level requires the students to read a considerable amount of English text sources beyond the instruction process. To make the reading process effective, higher-level learners should develop several reading skills. Firstly, it's the ability to analyze and evaluate the content critically. Next, readers must assess the credibility of sources, understand the author's perspective, and identify biases or assumptions. This involves questioning the text, distinguishing between main ideas and supporting details, seeking evidence, and drawing well-founded conclusions. Secondly, a broad and sophisticated vocabulary should be learned to understand complex texts. Higher-level readers must be acknowledged with technical terms, scientific language, and varied writing styles. What is more, language learners are to integrate information from multiple sources and perspectives. This skill is crucial for forming a comprehensive understanding of a topic, identifying connections between ideas, and constructing new insights.

Most studies indicate that students employ a variety of cognitive strategies to enhance their reading skills. Techniques such as skimming for a general overview, scanning for specific information, and re-reading for deeper understanding are commonly carried out in our university language lessons. Additionally, predicting, note-taking, identifying main ideas, recognizing synonyms and word families, annotating, and summarizing are valuable strategies for retaining and organizing information. Almasi and Susan (2003) focus attention on such reading strategies as evaluating content, connecting the text to prior knowledge or experiences, asking and answering relevant questions, identifying keywords, using grammatical analysis to understand sentence components, re-reading, paraphrasing, and summarizing. These reading strategies are particularly practiced by ESP students of cybernetics science studies. Thus, improving reading comprehension can be increased through suitable teaching methods and understanding the insight of reading skills and reading strategies.

Discussion and Results

In our ESP reading lessons, we observed that higher-level reading involves using specific strategies tailored to the text and purpose. What is more, higher-level reading requires a high level of engagement and intrinsic motivation. Students must be willing to invest the time and effort needed to research complex texts. A genuine interest in the subject matter and a desire to learn and grow intellectually can drive this engagement. Deci and Ryan (1991) highlighted the significance of learners' self-determination in the educational process. They mentioned that it has become increasingly evident that self-determination, through intrinsic motivation and autonomous internalization, leads to outcomes that are advantageous for both individuals and society.

In our classroom, we suggested students choose from the latest topics for research in technology and computer science one of their greatest concerns, and

read special articles completing different language tasks. Among various 100 topics, they picked out the most attractive to them ones: *AI and Robotics; Networking and security, High-performance computing, Programming languages, and software systems, Machine learning and neuron networks, How AI and deep learning are changing the healthcare industry, Role of the blockchain, How is open source competing with paid software?, Distributed Data Clustering, How successful is computer-aided learning? Hazards of computer viruses, Ethical hacking: white hat techniques, Is scrum methodology the best of best?* As a result, making their own choice, the undergraduates enjoyed reading more, seeking out new knowledge in authentic, sophisticated texts, and staying curious about the researched subject. That is to say, learners should be given greater freedom to choose what suits best their interests and needs including academic reading and professional-oriented texts.

The provided Professionally-Oriented Reading involved conducting the following Theme-Based tasks: identifying key terms, and main ideas, putting comprehension, discussion questions, and predicting future investigations and results in the topic. It is important to mention that Theme-Based Learning (TBL) is a model of Content-Based Instruction (CBI), which has been a prominent trend around the world in the past two decades showing the advantages of "emphasizing learning about something rather than learning about language", thus "the goal is to assist learners in developing general academic language skills through interesting and relevant content", Jason Cenozo stated in 2015. This model is definitely very suitable to use in English for Specific Purposes lessons as a need for training learners for particular contexts and events according to the academic matter and students' interests.

The most challenging task appeared to be writing a summary. Summarizing is a strategy that is often perceived as arduous. One of the biggest challenges in summary writing is distinguishing relevant knowledge from irrelevant information and identifying the main ideas of a text. Students often struggle to tell apart between crucial points and minor details, leading to summaries that are either too detailed or lacking essential information. They find it difficult to rephrase content concisely while maintaining the original message. Many students stumble with finding the right words to rephrase sentences while avoiding plagiarism. Students also often face difficulties in structuring their summaries logically, leading to disjointed and confusing narratives. Writing a clear and accurate summary requires a good command of grammar and syntax. Errors in sentence structure, punctuation, or word choice undermine the summary's clarity and effectiveness. Addressing these difficulties through targeted instruction and practice can help students develop their summarizing skills effectively. Reading extensively and proficiently contributes to better writing skills. Exposure to diverse writing styles and vocabulary through reading helps learners improve their own writing, making it more clear, concise, and impactful. Sufficient practice will build the required skill improvement, making students feel encouraged and motivated.

Conclusion

In today's fast-paced and ever-changing work environment, continuous learning is a necessity. Proficient readers can quickly assimilate new information from books, articles, and industry publications. This ability to stay updated with the latest trends, technologies, and best practices is crucial for professional growth and maintaining a competitive edge in one's field.

Reading proficiency improves critical thinking and analytical skills. By implementing context-specific, task-based strategies, coupled with a focus on student autonomy and interest, educators can significantly enhance students' reading comprehension and overall academic performance. Theme-based learning has proven to be an effective approach for developing both language skills and subject matter knowledge. By providing students with opportunities to explore topics of interest within their field, we can foster intrinsic motivation and deeper engagement with the reading material. The main challenges students face are distinguishing between main ideas and details, rephrasing content, and maintaining coherence.

The ESP teacher needs to investigate the IT genre, the language, and the skills concerning computer science communication. It is also essential to design an updated course, renovate teaching materials, obtain more recent and modern context materials, be aware of the latest developments in the world of science and technology, discover the IT students' specific interests, and conduct a needs analysis.

While this study sheds light on the importance of these strategies, further research is needed to investigate their long-term impact on students' professional careers. Additionally, exploring the effectiveness of these approaches in different cultural and educational contexts would be beneficial.

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